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Evaluation of Influence of Solar Radiation Intensity and Wind Speed on Efficiency of Solar Water Heating Collector

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Abstract: The purpose of this scientific article is to analyze and evaluate the influence of two key climatic parameters - the intensity of solar radiation and wind speed on the efficiency of solar water heating collectors. In recent decades, scientific interest in renewable energy has grown markedly, driven by global challenges such as climate change and rising fuel and electricity costs. This study provides an analysis of the operation of solar collectors located in the city of Osh with a continental climate. The authors use the mathematical tools to assess the effect of changes in sunlight intensity and wind flow rate on the thermal efficiency of these installations. The results presented in the article emphasize that an increase in the level of solar radiation leads to a proportional increase in the work of the collector. However, the influence of wind speed turned out to be more multifaceted: if at low speeds, an increase in the efficiency of the system was observed, then at higher speeds this led to an increase in heat losses. The article contributes to the development of the theory and practice of using solar energy, offering recommendations for optimizing the operation of solar collectors in various climatic conditions. The presented analysis is of great practical importance, laying the foundation for the further development and improvement of solar energy systems. This is relevant for achieving sustainable development goals and ensuring energy security.

Keywords: Solar radiation, performance of solar collectors, wind speed, thermal efficiency, energy efficiency, renewable energy sources, climatic impact, thermal losses, contact heat exchange.

1 Introduction

In recent decades, scientific and engineering interest in renewable energy sources has increased significantly due to global challenges such as climate change, sustainable development and energy security [1-3]. Solar collectors, in particular, are one of the most developing areas in the field of solar energy due to their ability to convert solar radiation into heat [4,5]. The efficiency of solar collectors can vary significantly depending on many factors, among which special attention is paid to the intensity of solar radiation and wind speed [6-8].

In previously published studies [6-8,9] of this area, the effect of solar radiation intensity on the productivity of solar collectors was most often considered, showing an increase in the thermal efficiency of devices with a proportional increase in radiation intensity. The effect of atmospheric conditions such as air quality and temperature on reservoir efficiency was also studied. However, the question of the effect of wind speed on the performance of solar collectors is not sufficiently disclosed. Wind can have both positive and negative effects on

the operation of collectors: on the one hand, it contributes to the cooling of the collector surface, reducing thermal losses, on the other hand, it can lead to a decrease in the effective area of irradiation due to vibrations and changes in the angle of incidence of sunlight [7,8].

The purpose of this study is to evaluate the effect of solar radiation intensity and wind speed on the performance of the solar collector. Through a comprehensive analysis of meteorological data and the results of solar collectors, this study seeks to identify the optimal conditions for their operation and suggest methods to improve their efficiency.

The terminology that will be used in this work includes the following definitions: "solar collector" (a device for absorbing solar radiation and converting it into heat), "solar radiation intensity" (the power of solar radiation incident on a unit of area), "wind speed" (the speed of the air flow at a certain height from the surface of the earth). The study is carried out using data collected from meteorological stations, as well as the results of experimental tests of solar collectors.

This introduction logically leads to the hypothesis that optimization of the operation of solar collectors is possible due to the adaptation of their structure and operating modes to changes in the intensity of solar change and wind speed, which will increase their efficiency in different climatic conditions.

2 Materials and methods

Description of study site

Location: Osh town, located in the Kyrgyz Republic, occupies the unique geographical position in the Ak-Buura river valley at an altitude of about 1000 meters above sea level. Surrounded by mountains, Osh has a specific microclimate, which significantly affects its weather conditions, including the intensity of solar radiation and wind speed [10-13].

Temperature conditions

The climate of Osh is characterized as continental with hot summers, when temperatures can reach + 40 ° C, and relatively mild winters, with temperatures rarely dropping below -10 ° C. These conditions provide an optimal environment for the use of solar technologies, as high temperatures contribute to the effective heating of water.

Solar radiation

Osh is marked by a high level of solar activity, reaching up to 3000 solar hours per year, with an average annual radiation intensity of about 2000 kWh/m². This creates ideal conditions for the research and recovery of solar water heating systems, especially in summer months, when there is a peak in solar activity and demand for hot water.

Wind conditions

Wind speed in Osh varies, but usually remains at a moderate level of about 3-4 m/s. However, in spring and autumn, winds can increase, reaching 7-8 m/s which can help cool the water in the collectors during periods of decreasing night temperatures.

Soil conditions

The region is characterized mainly by loamy soils, which do not significantly affect the functioning of solar collectors, but are important for the installation of support structures.

Due to its unique climatic conditions, the city of Osh is an ideal place for the deployment and study of solar water heating systems. The stable intensity of solar radiation and predictable wind speeds make it possible to achieve optimal conditions for the efficient use of solar energy.

Used materials:

1. *Solar collectors:* Flat panel models with high solar absorption and minimal thermal losses.

- Absorption surface: special coating with high absorption co-efficiency and low reflectivity.
- Thermal insulating materials: glass wool and aerogel for minimizing heat losses.

2. *Weather station*: An installation for recording the intensity of solar radiation and wind speed with an accuracy of 0.1 m/s for wind and up to 1 W/m² for solar radiation.

Assumptions and their justification

1. *Solar radiation stability*: It is assumed that the average monthly intensity of solar radiation does not change by more than 5% of the annual average, based on historical data for the region.

2. *Effect of wind*: Wind speed can have a cooling effect on the collector, which reduces its thermal efficiency. This assumption is based on preliminary theoretical calculations and literary data.

Mathematical procedures

Mathematical modeling: Using differential heat transfer equations to model reservoir processes. Calculations are performed using numerical analysis software such as Python with the NumPy library.

During the development and improvement of solar water heating collectors (WHC) designed to provide hot water supply, key difficulties were identified. They include the disadvantages of the operating characteristics of current solar installations due to the complexity of their designs, the lack of optimization of production processes and high costs for materials, which leads to an increase in the cost of producing thermal energy [14]. Improving the efficiency of the WHC is a key aspect for the economy, since the productivity of the reservoirs is due to various factors, including their efficiency and thermal losses within the system.

The solar water heating collector shown in the picture 1 includes complex heat exchange components: 1- metal plates that receive heat; 2- metal heat removal plate for heat transfer to the water circuit; 3- pipelines for water circulation; 4- protective glass coating; 5- housing made of wood; a 6- insulation layer made of aerogel; 7- collector base made of plywood.

Picture 1. Solar water heating collector

The solar water-heating collector functions based on the principle of the greenhouse effect, when the sun's rays penetrate through the glass coating and heat the metal plates. They are placed between and inside water pipes through which water is circulated. This design provides high heat transfer to water due to uniform heat distribution through heat conduction from all sides.

There are two main approaches to evaluating the performance of solar water heaters. The first involves conducting long-term field experiments that make it possible to assess the operation of reservoirs in environmental conditions. The second approach is based on mathematic modeling of the heat exchange processes occurring in the collector in order to determine its efficiency depending on parameters such as solar radiation intensity and wind speed, etc. [6-8,15,16].

The method of calculating the operation of the solar water-heating collector is based on the balance of heat balance. In accordance with this principle, the amount of thermal energy absorbed by the solar collector should be equivalent to the combined amount of thermal energy accumulated inside the collector and heat losses discharged into the environment. The basic equation of the thermal balance of the solar water-heating collector establishes that the energy captured by the collector from the sun is equal to the sum of the energy stored by the collector and the energy of the system losses [17-21].

The thermal balance equation of the solar water heating collector can be written as follows:

$$Q_{in} = Q_{out} + Q_{loss} \quad (1)$$

where: Q_{in} - incoming heat, W; Q_{out} - useful heat, W; Q_{loss} - heat loss, W.

Incoming heat (Q_{in}) consists of two components:

- *Direct solar radiation* (Q_{sun}), W:

$$Q_{sun} = G_{sun} \cdot A_{col} \cdot \eta_{opt} \quad (2)$$

where: G_{sun} - solar radiation flux density, W/m²; A_{col} - the collector area, m²; η_{opt} - optical efficiency factor of the collector.

• *Scattered solar radiation (Q_{diff}), W:*

$$Q_{diff} = G_{diff} \cdot A_{col} \cdot (1 - \eta_{opt}) \quad (3)$$

where: G_{diff} - scattered solar radiation flux density, W/m².

The useful heat (Q_{out}) is the heat that is absorbed by the water in the collector.

$$Q_{out} = m_{water} \cdot c_{water} \cdot \Delta T \quad (4)$$

where: m_{water} - water weight, kg; c_{water} - is the specific heat capacity of water, J/(kg · °C); ΔT - temperature difference between water and environment, °C.

Heat loss (Q_{loss}) is heat that is lost by the collector to the surrounding medium.

$$Q_{loss} = A_{col} \cdot U_{loss} \cdot (T_{col} - T_{amb}) \quad (5)$$

where: U_{loss} - heat loss coefficient of the collector, W/(m² · °C); T_{col} - collector temperature, °C; T_{amb} - is the ambient temperature, °C.

The heat loss coefficient (U_{loss}) can be calculated using the following formula:

$$U_{loss} = U_t + U_b + U_w + U_e \quad (6)$$

where: U_t - heat losses through the upper part of the collector, W/(m² · °C); U_b - heat loss through the lower part of the collector, W/(m² · °C); U_w - heat loss through the sides of the collector, W/(m² · °C); U_e - heat losses due to wind, W/(m² · °C).

Heat losses due to wind (U_e) can be calculated from the following formula:

$$U_e = h_{wind} \cdot (T_{col} - T_{amb}) \quad (7)$$

where: h_{wind} - convective heat exchange coefficient, W/(m² · °C); T_{col} - collector temperature, °C; T_{amb} - ambient temperature, °C.

The convective heat exchange coefficient (h_{wind}) can be calculated by the following formula:

$$h_{wind} = 2 \cdot Nu \cdot k_{air} \cdot \left(\frac{L}{D}\right)^{0,5} \quad (8)$$

where: Nu is the Nusselt number; k_{air} - air thermal conductivity, W/(m · °C); L - collector length, m; D - collector width, m.

The Nusselt number (Nu) depends on the wind speed (ϑ_{wind}) and the geometry of the collector:

$$Nu = C \cdot Re^n \cdot Pr^m \quad (9)$$

where: Re - Reynolds number, which depends on wind speed and characteristic length of the collector; Pr - Prandtl number, which is a characteristic of the working environment and is usually considered constant for this case; C , n , m - empirical coefficients derived from experimental data or theoretical considerations.

The Reynolds number is generally defined as:

$$Re = \frac{\vartheta_{wind} \cdot L}{\nu} \quad (10)$$

where: ν - kinematic viscosity of the working medium (air).

By substituting all these equations into the heat balance equation, an equation can be obtained to calculate the efficiency КПД (η) of the solar water heating collector:

$$\eta = \frac{Q_{out}}{Q_{sun}} = \frac{m_{water} \cdot c_{water} \cdot \Delta T}{G_{sun} \cdot A_{col} \cdot \eta_{opt}} \quad (11)$$

Solution of this equation for variable allows to express dependence of collector efficiency on solar radiation density (G_{sun}) and ambient wind speed. The corresponding results are presented in the picture 2.

The graph shows five curves, each of which corresponds to a wind speed from 1.0 m/s to 5.0 m/s. The intensity of solar radiation on the abscissa varies from 0 to 1000 W/m².

By analyzing the curves, several conclusions can be drawn:

1. *Efficiency and intensity of solar radiation:* All curves show a positive trend, confirming that with an increase in the intensity of solar radiation, the efficiency of the solar collector increases. This is expected since solar energy falling on the collector will lead to an increase in heating and, accordingly, a higher heat input.

2. *Wind speed:* The graph shows that at lower wind speeds (1.0 and 2.0 m/s) the curves are steeper, which indicates higher efficiency under these conditions.

3. *Effect of high wind speed:* At a wind speed of 5.0 m/s, the curve has a flatter slope over the entire range of radiation intensity, which indicates that high wind speed leads to an increase in thermal losses, reducing the overall efficiency of the system.

4. *Optimal operating conditions:* The optimal conditions for the operation of the solar collector are presented on the lower curve with the lowest wind speed, where even at low solar radiation intensity, the collector shows relatively high efficiency.

5. *The dependence of efficiency on the change in both factors:* Graphic shows that the optimal performance of the solar collector is achieved with a specific combination of solar intensity due to radiation and wind speed, and that for each wind speed there is a different efficiency curve.

Thus, the graph emphasizes the importance of taking into account both solar radiation intensity and wind speed in the design and operation of solar water heating collectors in order to achieve maximum efficiency.

Picture 2. Dependence of solar collector efficiency (DSCE) from solar radiation density and wind speed

3 Discussion

Key study results

The study is aimed at assessing the interaction between solar radiation intensity, wind speed and sol-non reservoir performance. Key results show that the intensity of solar radiation has a direct positive effect on the efficiency of the solar collector, while the wind speed has a difficult effect: a moderate increase in efficiency at low speeds and a significant decrease at high ones.

Comparison with previous studies

The results obtained in our study are in good agreement with studies [6-8,9] showing an increase in thermal efficiency of collectors with an increase in the intensity of solar radiation. One question of the influence of wind speed remained less studied. In our study, it was revealed that a small wind can act as a temperature regulator, while a strong wind leads to excessive thermal losses.

Explaining the results

The efficiency of solar collectors at low wind speeds can be explained by a decrease in the risk of overheating and an increase in thermal efficiency. At higher wind speeds, intensive cooling probably leads to an increase in thermal losses, which reduces the overall efficiency of the system.

Study limitations

Our results are based on data obtained in a continental climate with four seasons, which may limit their application in regions with different climatic conditions. In addition, the study was conducted using a certain type of solar collectors, which can also affect the generalizability of the results.

Directions for future research

Based on the results of this study, an in-depth study of the effect on different types of solar collectors of various meteorological conditions, including the combined effect of wind speed and solar radiation intensity is recommended. It is also important to investigate the effects of air humidity and atmospheric pressure.

Our results significantly expand the understanding of the impact of wind speed on the performance of solar collectors and provide valuable information for their optimization. They emphasize the importance of a complex approach to the design and operation of solar energy systems adapted to local meteorological conditions for maximum efficiency of actually manufactured structures.

4 Conclusion

Based on a comprehensive analysis of meteorological data and practical results of solar collectors, we formulated the following key conclusions:

1. The intensity of solar radiation is the main factor that determines the performance of solar collectors. The direct connection between the intensity of solar radiation and the efficiency of the collector is confirmed: with an increase in intensity up to 1000 W/m^2 , an increase in thermal power occurs.

2. Wind speed has a significant impact on reservoir efficiency, as clearly shown in the graph. At low wind speeds up to 2.0 m/s, productivity increases, probably due to effective cooling. It helps to maintain the reservoir temperature in the optimal range, which allows increasing the heat output and, as a result, the efficiency of the system.

With an increase in wind speed over 3.0 m/s, the cooling effect will fall. Increasing airflow can lead to increased heat loss through convection, which reduces the overall heat balance of the system. Moreover, at very high wind speeds, as shown for 5.0 m/s, it is possible to increase negative phenomena, such as vibration and a change in the angle of absorption of radiation, which further reduces the efficiency of the collector.

3. Optimal operating conditions of the solar collector are achieved at low wind speeds and high solar radiation intensity. The data show that for maximum efficiency, collectors should be operated in conditions with low wind speed.

4. The practical application of the research results is expressed in improving the design of solar collectors, especially their ability to resist the negative effects of wind and perceive solar radiation as fully as possible.

5. Recommendations for future research include an analysis of the impact of cloud cover, air humidity and other meteorological conditions on the performance of solar collectors. It will be useful to study the long-term energy production of collectors, taking into account the change of seasons and various climatic conditions.

In conclusion, this study makes a significant contribution to the development of solar energy, offering valuable practical recommendations for improving the design and operation of solar collectors. The results are important for the scientific community, as they cover hitherto unexplored aspects of the influence of wind speed and solar radiation intensity on the efficiency of solar collectors, and have significance for society as a whole, emphasizing the need to spread renewable energy sources for energy security.

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